

EXAMINING THE MEDIATING ROLE OF ADVERTISING ON BRAND PERSONALITY AND CONSUMER PURCHASE DECISION

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Abstract

Brand personality is an attractive and pleasant concept in today's marketing. Acker (1991) has described it as one of the core dimensions of brand identity and the closest variable to the consumer's decision-making process for purchasing. This study investigated the mediating phenomenon of advertising on brand personality and the purchase decision of club athletes of Iran from Majid Sport brand. The method of present research is descriptive-correlation, using structural equation modeling. The statistical population of the research was the athletes of Iran's clubs in 2023, and 217 consumers of Majid brand products were selected by random sampling. The data collection tool consisted of four questionnaires, including: A) Questionnaire on the demographic characteristics of the subjects. B) Advertising mediation questionnaire with one question and five components about how athletes get to know the Majid brand, (the components include of television, radio, internet, telephone, oral survey), C) Acker's standard questionnaire with 30 items and five components (honesty, passion and excitement, competence, perfection, strength and stability) on a five-point Likert scale,

D) Standard purchase decision questionnaire of Sproles and Kendall (1986) which has 14 items and 3 components (attitude towards the brand willingness to buy, familiarity with the brand) based on the Likert measurement scale. The results of the factor analysis of the customer's purchase decision questionnaire showed that the customer's purchase decision from three dimensions (attitude towards the brand, willingness to buy, and familiarity with the brand) is effective on the customer's purchase decision. The results of the factor analysis of the brand personality questionnaire showed that the factors affecting the brand personality from five dimensions (honesty, passion and excitement, competence, perfection, strength and stability) are effective on the brand personality. The extent of the effect of brand personality on the purchase decision without advertisements showed: with 95% certainty, brand personality is effective on the purchase decision. Examining the simultaneous influence of brand personality on customers' purchase decisions showed that: with 95% certainty brand personality and advertisements are effective on purchase decisions. The indicators of the model of the effect of brand personality on the purchase decision with the mediation role of advertising showed that advertising has no effect on the brand personality and the mediation role of advertising is effective on the purchase decision. In addition, the brand personality is effective in the purchase decision through the advertising mediation.

Keywords: Advertising Mediation, Brand Personality, Purchase Decision, Athletes, Majid Sport Brand

1. INTRODUCTION

The terminology "brand" is like capital that creates value for the organization and its products, therefore, promoting the brand in many cases becomes the strategy of the organization. A brand is an image of products in the market. People who deal with brand are looking for certain qualities or characteristics that make it special or unique (Ries,2019).

A brand has power when it can influence the behavior of consumers who look at that brand and make the preferences, tendencies and purchase behavior for that brand repetitive and every day. Today, the brand is an important part of marketing strategy, and brand marketing is at the heart of business, and many of the world's best-known companies, such as Praktrand, Gamble, and March, are structured around their brand (Baker et al., 2009).

The most obvious and well-known way to create a brand personality is to use a celebrity endorser. Public heroes, sports figures, pop stars, and movie stars are hired to lend their personality to a brand for a long time, and the practice continues to grow. However, essentially all advertising influences brand personality and consumer purchase decisions, not just when an endorser is used (Girish, 2008). Sports equipment manufacturers are among the companies that use advertising to introduce their brand personality to consumers. Advertisements create an emotional image of the brand personality, and brand personality correlates provide depth of emotion and desire to connect. In this way, brand personality can make a brand more attractive and memorable and turn it into a means to express the customer's identity. Considering the above discussion, it can be determined that advertising or market communication helps to build brand personality, and this is when the consumer associates human characteristics with the products, and this creates brand personality for consumers (Zable,2010). In general, identifying a suitable market and starting a meaningful relationship using appropriate and entertaining content is an instant tactic for building loyal customers on the part of brand owners (Homburg, 2010). Companies like Majid brand may choose to present advertisements in more attractive dimensions for the quick cognitive reactions of customers and optimally use the mediation of advertisements to attract consumers and introduce the personality of their brand. Therefore, according to the mentioned topics, the researcher in this research seeks to answer this question: Does mediating advertising have an effect on the brand personality and purchasing decision of athletes? Leung et al. (2012) investigated the effect of customer loyalty on consumer buying behavior, which they did on 350 male customers in Malaysia, and concluded that there is a significant relationship between brand equity, satisfaction, and consumer purchase loyalty, and they state that consumer satisfaction is an introduction to their loyalty. They also showed that although brand equity has less relationship in comparison with consumer satisfaction and loyalty, brand equity is considered a positive point for the brand. Shu Ying-woo (2011) In a research titled investigating the relationship between the level of consumer involvement and the effectiveness of advertising, it was

found that the level of individual involvement is a very important variable in determining the advertising strategy, because there is a direct relationship between the level of consumer involvement and the importance of the content of advertising. This research also showed that there is a positive relationship between the degree of consumer involvement and the hierarchy of effectiveness of any advertisement.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method of present research is descriptive-correlation, using structural equation modeling. The statistical population of the research was the athletes of Iran's clubs in 2023, and 217 consumers of Majid brand products were selected by random sampling. The data collection tool consisted of four questionnaires, including: A) Questionnaire on the demographic characteristics of the subjects. B) Advertising mediation questionnaire with one question and five components about how athletes get to know the Majid brand, (the components include of television, radio, internet, telephone, oral survey), C) Acker's standard questionnaire with 30 items and five components (honesty, passion and excitement, competence, perfection, strength and stability) on a five-point Likert scale, D) Standard purchase decision questionnaire of Sproles and Kendall (1986) which has 14 items and 3 components (attitude towards the brand willingness to buy, familiarity with the brand) based on the Likert measurement scale.

Table 1. The question of the effect of advertising mediation

How did you get acquainted with the brand (Majid)?	TV	Radio	Phone	Oral
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3. FINDINGS

Table2. Descriptive statistics of brand personality questionnaire

Variables	Numbers	Mean	Standard Deviation
Honesty	217	3/14	0/44
Passion	217	3/97	0/57
competence	217	3/58	0/56
perfection	217	3/41	0/55
strength and stability	217	3/36	0/27

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of consumer purchasing decisions

Variables	Numbers	Mean	Standard Deviation
Attitude towards the brand	217	3/04	0/34
Purchase Intention	217	3/28	0/47
Familiarity with Brand	217	3/18	0/36

Model of the effect of brand personality on purchase decision through advertising mediation:

Chi-Square=191.12, df=63, P-value=0.00000, RMSEA=0.128

Figure 1. Model of the effect of brand personality on purchase decision through advertising mediation

Chi-Square=191.12, df=63, P-value=0.00000, RMSEA=0.128

Figure 2. Path analysis of Model of the effect of brand personality on purchase decision through advertising mediation

Table 4. fit indices of the research model

NO.	Indices	Value	Appropriate Value	Status
1	χ^2	191/12	-	-
2	RMR	0/051	0/05Less than	Near to optimal
3	CFI	0/90	Equal or more than 0.90	optimal
4	IFI	0/90	Equal or more than 0.90	optimal
5	NFI	0/89	more than 0.90	Near to optimal
6	GFI	0/95	more than 0.90	optimal
7	AGFI	0/92	more than 0.90	optimal
8	RMSEA	0/128	Less than 0.1	Near to optimal
9	CMIN/DF	3	Between 2 to 3	optimal

The results of the table show that the indices of the ratio of chi-square to the degree of freedom CMIN/DF are equal to 3, the absolute fit index RMR is equal to 0.051, the comparative fit indices CFI and IFI are equal to 0.90, the goodness of fit index GFI equal to 0.95 and the RMSEA index equal to 0.128 are in the optimal and acceptable level, which means that the current research model has a good fit and the factor structure considered for it is acceptable.

Table 5. The effect of brand personality on purchase decision mediated by advertising

Objective	Path coefficient	T statistic	Result
Effect of advertising on brand personality	0/001	00/001	Not approved
Effect of advertising on purchase decision	0/61	13	Approved
The effect of brand personality on purchase decision mediated by advertising	0/34	6/21	Approved

According to the table, indices of the model shows that advertising has no effect on brand personality and mediating advertising is effective on the purchase decision with a factor loading of 0.61 and a T-statistic equal to 13. Also, the brand personality is effective on the purchase decision with the mediation of advertisements with a factor load of 0.34 and a T-statistic of 6.21.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The findings of the research showed that advertising mediation has an effect on the brand personality and the purchase decision of the athletes of the clubs. The main contribution of this study includes three main dimensions. The first dimension is in the context of the relationship between advertising mediation and brand personality, and the findings indicated that advertising mediation has a significant and direct relationship with dimensions (honesty, competence, perfection) of brand personality, and only in the dimension (strength and stability, passion and excitement) of Majid brand, no significant relationship was observed. The second dimension in the context of the mediating relationship between advertisements and consumers' intention to

purchase sports products of Majid brand is that the results showed a direct and significant relationship between advertising mediating and consumers' purchase decision in dimensions (attitude towards the brand, willingness to buy, familiarity with the brand). In the context of the third dimension, it is in the field of the subjects' familiarity with the Majid sports brand that the findings of the research showed that most of the subjects were acquainted with this brand through television advertisements. Advertising mediation is used in the process of creating a brand personality. Basically, all advertising affects brand personality, not just when an endorsement is used. In the process of creating brand personality, especially in sports brands, in advertising and marketing, communication methods are widely used to create brand personality. Many researchers, including Erdoğan and Baker, found that brands are sensitive to communications and references that catalyze consumer behavior. It may be seen in some studies that a general model of advertising is integrated with a model of character building for the brand. The meaning of brand personality is the emotional aspect of the brand image in people's minds. This image is formed from all the experiences that the consumer has of a brand, and it can include dimensions (enthusiasm and excitement, competence, perfection, attitudinal loyalty, honesty) that are promoted by advertising with different media (TV, radio, internet, by phone, orally) are introduced to consumers. Advertisements play an effective role in the formation of brand personality.

Successful brands like Majid sports brand have the opportunity to eventually gain a leadership position. This state is presented in advertisements as a stimulus for the superiority of the product. The brand's strong and stable position can be built and based on the elements of high sales. This message should be presented in a unified manner in all marketing activities. There are two main elements in the brand personality, which are: the type of benefit that is assigned by the brand and the type of consumer that values it.

Advertisements that do not try to do anything more than providing product specifications, mainly try to attract the rationality of customers and focus more on sales proposals or show ideas such as the difference between the current brand and competitors. The personality of the brand which is built through advertising creates an emotional image of the brand from which the personality of the brand is formed, and then it will lead to the creation of love and interest in these relationships in consumers, therefore, the mediation of advertising can make the personality of the brand more attractive and make it more memorable and become a means to intensify good feelings in the consumer. According to these contents, it can be said that advertising or market communication help to build brand personality; Provided that the consumer finds human characteristics associated with the advertised product. The results of the present research are in line with the findings of the research of Leung and colleagues (2012), Shu Ying-woo in (2001) that concluded that there is a positive relationship between the degree of consumer involvement and the effectiveness hierarchy of any advertising. Philip Jones (2006) indicates that Advertising in the short term increases the number of consumers of products. The results are also in line with Zhu & Chen research (2010) that indicates hotels often use advertising, communicating with customers and marketing their services to promote their brand.

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